

DEVELOPMENT AND CHARACTERIZATION OF NOVEL BIOCOMPOSITES OF THERMOPLASTIC BIOPOLYMERS REINFORCED WITH CARBON NANOFIBER AND CARBON NANOTUBES

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SUMMARY

This study describes and discusses the morphological, thermal, mechanical, electrical conductivity and barrier properties of novel nanobicomposites of PCL reinforced with Carbon Nanotubes and Carbon Nanofibers. The main conclusion from this work is that carbon nanotubes and nanofibers can be used to enhance the conductivity, thermal, mechanical but, interestingly, also to enhance gas barrier properties of thermoplastic biopolyesters.

Keywords: Biopolymers, nanocomposites, carbon nanotubes, carbon nanofibers.

INTRODUCTION

Biodegradable polymers have received considerable attention due to their potential applications in fields related to environmental protection and ecology in the last two decades. Most biodegradable polymers have excellent properties comparable to many petroleum-based plastics. These materials possess a number of excellent and promising properties that can be used in a number of applications, including packaging, automotive and biomedical sectors. Thermoplastic biodegradable polymers, such as polyhydroxyalkanoate (PHA) and polycaprolactones (PCL), are processable using conventional plastics machinery. PCL is a thermoplastic biodegradable polyester synthesized by chemical conversion of crude oil. PCL has good water, oil, solvent, and chlorine resistance, a low melting point, and low viscosity, and is easily processed using conventional melt blending technologies (1). PCL is at this time being investigated for its use in biomedical utensils, pharmaceutical controlled release systems, and in biodegradable packaging (2).

So, biodegradable polymers have great commercial potential for bio-plastic. However, these material exhibit low toughness, low heat distortion temperature, high gas permeability, low melt viscosity, low thermal and electrical conductivity. These shortcomings restrict their use in a wide-range of applications. Reinforcement of these materials using nanoparticles may be an effective way to improve these properties (3-5).

There are research studies showing improvement in the biodegradable material with the addition of carbon nanotubes. Reinforcement of some of PCL with carbon nanotubes

has previously been carried out with the overall aim of increasing its biodegradation rate and to enhance mechanical properties, i.e. this route led to considerable improvements in the composites tensile strength (6). Other authors reported that the addition of small amount of MWCNT into PCL matrix can improve its thermal stability (7). Saeed and Park reported that the conductivity of the nanocomposite of PCL increases with the increase of CNT content. (8).

However, to the best of our knowledge there is no prior work on the use of carbon nanotubes and carbon nanofibers to modify the barrier properties of these polymers against the absorption of gases and water vapour. In this first study, the morphology, thermal, conductivity, mechanical and solvent barrier properties as a function of filler content of biocomposites of PCL containing carbon nanotubes or nanofibers as reinforcing elements are studied.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Morphological results

For example, Figure 1A shows the film of PCL with 1 wt.-% of CNF. From this Figure it can be seen that the CNF are highly embedded and dispersed in the matrix supporting the existence of a good adhesion between matrix and filler. However, with the increase in CNF contents (Figure 1B) filler agglomeration begins to occur.

Electrical and Thermal conductivity

The electrical conductivities of the biodegradable materials with carbon nanotubes and carbon nanofibers were tested, and the results are shown in Figure 2. With the increase in CNT and CNF loading, the electrical conductivity of the PCL nanocomposite was seen to increase, which is attributed to the high electrical conductivity and good dispersion of the CNT and CNF. The electrical conductivity of the nanocomposites of carbon nanotubes is higher than the nanocomposite with carbon nanofiber. The electrical conductivity of the nanocomposites increased from 2.4×10^{-6} S/cm for PCL with 1 wt.-% CNT to 0.33 S/cm for PCL with 10 wt.-% CNT. In the case of carbon nanofibers the electrical conductivity increases also with the increase of carbon nanofiber up to value of 0.10 S/cm for PCL with 10 wt.-% CNF.

The thermal conductivity of carbon materials is dominated by atomic vibrations or phonons. Thermal conductivity of all the samples with carbon nanotubes and carbon nanofibers was measured by nanoflash equipment. The thermal diffusion was calculated by the Radiant Method and the Cowan Method for all the samples (see Figure 3). Thermal diffusion of the pure PCL it can't be calculated, possibly due to the low value. A reduction of the thermal diffusion of around 160% was observed in the PCL with 10 wt.-% CNT compared to the PCL+1 wt.-% CNT. In the case of the nanocomposite with carbon nanofibers, a reduction of around 165% was observed in the film PCL+10 wt.-% CNF compared with the film PCL+1 wt.-% CNF.

Mass transport properties

Water uptake of PCL and their nanocomposite were tested. The results of the water uptake are showed in Figure 4.

From the results, a reduction in water uptake of ca. 45% is observed in the PCL with 1 wt.-% carbon nanotube content compared with the unfilled biopolymer. It can be seen a reduction of the water uptake up to 50% in the case of the PCL+3 wt.-% CNT, however with the increase of CNT content the reduction of the water uptake decrease slowly. PCL with 5 and 10 wt.-% CNT show a reduction of water uptake of ca. 40% and 41% compared with the unfilled material.

For the PCL with carbon nanofibers, is observed in the Figure 4 the same behavior of the PCL with carbon nanotubes. Figure 4 teaches that water uptake show minimum values for specimens with 1 and 3 wt.-% carbon nanofiber content. Further increase in fiber content results in slighter improved water uptake to values. Films of PCL with 1 and 3wt.-% carbon nanofiber content have a water uptake decrease of 62% and 67% compared to the unfilled material, whereas films of PCL with 10 wt.-% carbon nanofiber content show a water permeability reduction of ca. 57%.

So, increasing carbon nanotubes or carbon nanofibers content was seen to result in fiber agglomeration and this is thought to cause a reduction in matrix homogeneity and cohesion and lead to preferential penetrant paths and to detrimental effects in barrier properties.

In Table 1 are summarized the oxygen permeability of the biodegradables PCL and their nanocomposites with carbon nanotubes and carbon nanofibers measured at 80%RH.

An observation from Table 1, the reported value of oxygen permeability for the PCL is $1.9e^{-18}m^3m/sm^2Pa$ measured at 0%RH (4) lower than the value measured at 80%RH in the laboratory is $7.06e^{-18}m^3m/sm^2Pa$, the difference could be related for the difference relativity humidity used for the testing. For the films of PCL, it can be observed a reduction of oxygen permeability of ca. 52%, 38%, 8% and 10% for the films with 1, 3, 5 and 10 wt.-% of Carbon nanotubes, respectively, compared with the unfilled material (see Figure 6). Increasing carbon nanotubes contents the oxygen permeability reduction decrease, due to the agglomeration of the carbon nanotubes. This observation is similar than the results of the water uptake and corroborated the morphology observation.

In the case of carbon nanofibers, films of PCL with 1, 3, 5 and 10 wt.-% carbon nanofibers reduce the oxygen permeability of ca. 26%, 29%, 25% and 25%, respectively, compared with the unfilled material (see Figure6).

As a result, the increased barrier properties, water and oxygen transmission, and conductivity and mechanical properties, suggests a great potential of the biodegradable PCL with 1 wt.-% carbon nanotubes and nanofibers composite films, in the applications including medicine, aerospace engineering, public transportation and food and beverage packaging.

Figure 1. SEM picture of: A) 1 wt.-% of CNTubes in PCL. Scale markers are 4 μ m and B) 5 wt.-% of CNTubes in PCL. Scale markers are 6 μ m.

Figure 2. Conductivity measurements of the neat film of neat PCL and of their nanobiocomposites with 1, 3, 5 and 10 wt.-% of the carbon nanotubes and carbon nanofibers prepared by solvng casting

Figure 3. Thermal diffusion coefficient (mm^2/s) of samples of neat PCL and of their nanobiocomposites with 1, 5 and 10 wt.-% of the carbon nanotubes and carbon nanofibers measured by Radiation and Cowan Method.

Figure 4. A) Water uptake of neat PCL and of their nanobiocomposites with 1, 3, 5 and 10 wt.-% of the carbon nanotubes and carbon nanofibers.

Table 1. Oxygen permeability for PCL and their nanocomposites

	P oxygen (m³ m/s m² Pa) at 80%RH
PCL	7.06 e ⁻¹⁸
PCL+1%CNT	3.39 e ⁻¹⁸
PCL+3%CNT	4.41 e ⁻¹⁸
PCL+5%CNT	6.51 e ⁻¹⁸
PCL+10%CNT	6.36 e ⁻¹⁸
PCL+1%CNF	5.23 e ⁻¹⁸
PCL+3%CNF	5.03 e ⁻¹⁸
PCL+5%CNF	5.27 e ⁻¹⁸
PCL+10%CNF	5.33e ⁻¹⁸
Literature value PCL	^{4a} 1.9e ⁻¹⁸

^a At 0%RH(solvent casting)

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